

Flavonoids from Lemon & Tea as Effective Inhibitors against Carcinogenesis

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Cancer is an anomalous proliferation of cells that manifests as pain, deformity and damage to the entire physiological device of the patient. Cancer can occur at any time, at any age and in any part of the body due to an intricate, partially understood chemistry between genes and the environmental factors. It continues to represent the largest cause of mortality claiming ≥ 3500 lives per million per annum around the world. A number of chemo-preventive agents are being used to treat cancer; >1500 anticancer drugs are under development and more than 500 drugs are under clinical trials. However, a safe and effective drug, against the deadly disease, is still miles away from our reach.

Medicinal plants serve as natural therapeutic agent against cancer. They stimulate host resistance against septicity by re-stabilizing body equilibrium and acclimatizing the body tissues. *Camellia sinensis* (Tea) is one of the most prevalent beverages in the world. Tea reduces the probability of cancers in ovary, oral cavity, colon, stomach and prostate owing to the presence of catechins (flavonoids). Catechin work as a strong antioxidant, impedes cell proliferation and modulates carcinogenic metabolism. Similarly, *Citrus limona* (lemon fruit) holds flavonoid, limonoid, nobiletin and tangeretin. The flavonoid, nobiletin and tangeretin are strong inhibitors of lump progression and trigger the detoxifying P₄₅₀ enzyme system.

Antioxidants, viz. vitamins (A,C,E), carotene, enzymes (superoxidase dismutase, catalase and glutathion peroxidase), minerals (Cu, Mn, Se and Zn), polysaccharides, polyphenols, flavonoids (quercetin, anthocyanins, catechins, flavones, flavonones and isoflavones), lignins, xanthenes, etc., thus play a substantial role in inhibition of carcinogenesis. Efforts are underway to combine the bioactive components of these plants to deduce their synergistic effects.

Key Words: Anti-oxidants, Bioactive Compound, Carcinogenesis, Chemotherapy, Flavonoids.

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